

GSM BASED SOLDIER TRACKING SYSTEM AND MONITORING USING WIRELESS COMMUNICATION

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Submitted: May 27, 2017 Accepted: June 15, 2017 Published: Sep 1, 2017

Abstract- To design a soldier tracking system using wireless system for monitoring the parameters of soldier are as Body temperature & Temperature. Biomedical sensors: Here to find the health status of soldier we are using a body temp sensor to measure body temperature as well as pulse rate sensor. These parameters are then signal conditioned and will be stored in the memory. One of the fundamental challenges in military operations lays in that the Soldier not able to communicate with control room administrator. In addition, each organization needs to enforce certain administrative and operational work when they interact over the network owned and operated by other organizations. Thus, without careful planning and coordination, one troop cannot communicate with the troops or leverage the communication infrastructure operated by the country troops in the same region. The purpose of this investigation was to test the components of the Soldier Tracking and Performance Measurement System against the statement of requirements as found in the Request for Proposal. Secondary aims of this investigation included gathering data that will allow potential users of the system to understand its capabilities and limitations, as well as allow efficient planning of both time and resources necessary to ensure efficient and productive use of the system for training the soldier.

Index terms: temperature sensor, pulse rate sensor, Soldier Tracking and Performance Measurement System

I. INTRODUCTION

In today's world enemy warfare is an important factor in nation's security. The national security mainly depends on army (ground), navy (sea), air-force (air). The important and vital role is played by the army soldier's. There are many concerns regarding the safety of these soldiers. As soon as any soldier enters the enemy lines it is very vital for the army base station to know the location as well as the health status of all soldiers. In our project we have come up with an idea of tracking the soldier as well as to give the health status of the soldier during the war, which enables the army personnel to plan the war strategies. By using the location sent by the GPS modem, the base station can understand the position of soldier. A GPS system can be defined as a device which would help to track the man or a vehicle with no human intervention at all. So far these vehicles have found applications in various fields such as military, vehicles, maps to find way, etc. This project is intended towards representing the problems faced by the soldier in the war field in a format to help the soldier to get a better solution. The problem that a soldier undergoes, difficult for the control station to perceive. The DRDO has taken steps to circumvent the problems of the soldier to keep moving forward in the war field. In this we have come with new ideas in order to help the soldier [3,4,5].

II. Literature Survey

Umar Farooq et al., [1] had proposed about the public safety in Punjab province Pakistan. They use a 4 stage safety sms system to survey and protect the people's lives. Thuong Le -Tien, Vu Phung [2] had proposed the tracking of vehicles on large outdoor area environment based on GPS and GSM system. With the support of modules the GPS receiver gets to know the exact location and gets the message and gets updates on the google maps. The current technology being used in our work had [9] proposed remote monitoring the soldiers with GPRS based protection system. It measures the heart beat rate, pressure range, temperature range and compared with the actual value stored in the EPROM. If any Discrepancy occurs, and then ARM7 processor will shift the control over to the relief system such as automatic Injection system and Vibrotactile system to simulate The oxygen pumping and also Transmit the Bio-Signals to the base station through GPRS.

Anto bennet et al. [6] had proposed that, it is due to the driver's fatigue, traffic accidents keep with a yearly increasing of a high rate. This paper shows the new fatigue detection

algorithms & techniques using eye blink, alcohol, impact, gas, etc. Sensors. In this technique the fatigue will be detected immediately and regular traps the events driver and third party. Through research presented in this work, we propose an intelligent car system for accident prevention and making the world a much better and safe place to Live.

Designed work had proposed to transmit the data which is sensed from Remote soldier to the server PC by using wireless transmission technology S. It is completely integrated so that it is possible to track anytime from anywhere. It has real-time capability. The accuracy of system is affected by some factors such as weather, environment around the mobile soldier unit, GPS receiver. The future works include optimizing the hardware system, choosing suitable GPS receiver. Improving the routing algorithm can be improved by network. This system has many advantages such as large capability, wide area strange, low operation costs, effective, strong expandability and easy to use. Upgrading this setup is very easy which makes it open to future a requirement which also makes it more efficient.

Anto bennet et al.,[7] had proposed the work is an attempt to design tracking system using GPS and GSM modem. The system is a TELEMONITORING SYSTEM. A software package is developed to READ, ANALYZE and PROCESS the received messages and store them. A communication is instantaneous therefore we can receive running report quickly. So once it is implemented it can track vehicles or humans any time. Anto bennet et al.,[8] this proposed system the authors about the public safety in Punjab province Pakistan. They use a 4 stage safety sms system to survey and protect the peoples lives. By using the four modules we will be able to track the vehicles. Anto bennet et al.,[6] describes tracking of vehicles on large outdoor area environment based on GPS and GSM system. With the support of modules the GPS receiver gets to know the exact location and gets the message and gets updates on the google maps

III. Proposed Work

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Fig 1. Block Diagram of soldier tracking system using wireless system

Here to find the health status of soldier we are using a body temperature sensor as well as pulse rate sensor. These sensors will measure the body temperature and the pulse rate of soldier and will be stored in microcontroller memory .The block diagram is shown in fig 1. The various parameters such as heart beat, pulse rate is obtained from the through the sensors attached to the body on receiving these parameters is first amplified to eliminate the noise and get a clear output signal .the amplified signal is send to the microcontroller 89s52 this is a very efficient microcontroller, 4 pins are used to control the entire system out of 40 pins. The pins according to the coding in the xilinx the 4 pins are named as mes1, mes2, mes3, mes4 (i.e.) message bit 1, message bit 2, and message bit 3 and 4.

The 4 pins receives the parameters and sends to various pins in the 89s51 and process the signal .The processed signal from the microcontroller is sent to the zigbee transmitter through MAX 232 or RS 232 which is a cable for transmitting and receiving the signals .

The signal is sent to the control station by zigbee transmitter the format of message received by control station is shown in fig 1.on receiving this message the control unit immediately responds by sending a reply message to crew or a soldier who is in panic our terrible situation to get him out of that place in our proposed system we have put forth two extra events .If the soldier gets caught in the enemy camp he has to immediately deactivate the system so , a deactivation is provided .in order to avoid the enemy crew members to access our tracking system a password is given to the soldier (e.g.) (xxyyzzz). The camera is also provided to check and get the terrain information

IV. Army Unit

Upon receiving the SMS, the visual basic software Sorts the solder's location based on the GPS coordinates also the health Status is displayed. In this way the army official's can keep a track of all their soldiers shown in fig 2.

Fig 2: Army Unit

Fig 3: Temperature sensors &Heart beat sensors

V. Temperature sensor and heart bea sensor

This temperature sensor is used to sense the temperature of the body this parameter is used to calibrate the entire temperature of the body .Through this it is helpful to know the status of the soldier. With the help of the heart beat sensor we are able to calculate the heart beat of the soldier shown in fig 3..

i) **GPS**

The Global Positioning System (GPS) is a space Based global navigation satellite system that provides reliable location and time information in all weather and at all times and anywhere on or near the Earth when and where there is an unobstructed line of sight to four or more GPS satellitesshown in fig 4.

Fig 4:GPS

Fig 5 Amplifier

ii) Amplifier

An electronic amplifier, amplifier, or (informally) amp is an electronic device that increases the power of a signal. It does this by taking energy from a power supply and controlling the output to match the input signal shape but with larger amplitude. In this sense, an amplifier modulates the output of the power supply to make the output signal stronger than the input signal. An amplifier is effectively the opposite of an attenuator: while an amplifier provides gain, an attenuator provides loss shown in fig 5.

iii) ZIGBEE

Zigbee is a specification which suites , high-level communication used to create a personal area network Zigbee is based on the IEEE.802.15.4 standard Zigbee transmission distance is 10-100 meters Zigbee has the defined rate of 250kb/sec. Zigbee specification is simpler and less expensive when compared to other wireless personal area networks such as BLUETOOTH and WIFI shown in fig 6.

Fig 6 Zigbee

Fig 7 Transformer

iv) Transformer

This is the step down transformer, which step downs the 220 volt AC to 12 AC .It act as a main source of power supply. It serves the purpose of tapped windings. Safe wiring techniques for power cords shown in fig 7.

Message Format

FIG 8;Message Format

This fig 8 is an example message format received to the control station;

VI. Experimental Results

FIG 9: Control Unit

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FIG 10: Temperature Measurement

This figure 9 shows the example dialogue box that will appear in the control unit .This message shows that the soldier temperature is normal and pulse rate is in good condition and there is no sign of war proceedings .This dialogue box was developed in the XCTC software and the program for this is done with the help of(KEIL VERSION 4).

The figure10 shows the dialogue box information that the soldier temperature is ABNORMAL .This temperature is measured and calibrated using the TEMPERATURE SENSOR .This message is received by the control unit and this indicates that the soldier's temperature is abnormal

Fig 11: GSM

Fig 12: Pulse Rate

This figure 11 shows that in the field the war has broke and the riot has started .This message indicates that the solider need some help in the war field. figure 12 shows that the soldier's pulse rate is down. This message shows that the solider need some help from control unit

VII. Conclusion

From the above designed work can be concluded that we are able to transmit the data which is sensed from remote soldier to the server PC by using wireless transmission technology GSM. It is completely integrated so that it is possible to track anytime from anywhere. It has real-time capability. The accuracy of system is affected by some factors Such as weather, environment around the mobile soldier unit, GPS receiver. The future works include optimizing the hardware system, choosing a suitable GPS receiver improving the routing algorithm can be improved by neural network. This system has many advantages such as large Capability, wide areas range, low operation costs, effective, strong expandability and easy to use. Upgrading this setup is very easy which makes it open to future a requirement.

REFERENCES

- [1] Aizat Azmi, Ahmad Amsyar Azman, Sallehuddin Ibrahim, and Mohd Amri Md Yunus, "Techniques In Advancing The Capabilities Of Various Nitrate Detection Methods: A Review", International Journal on Smart Sensing and Intelligent Systems., VOL. 10, NO. 2, June 2017, pp. 223-261.
- [2] Tsugunosuke Sakai, Haruya Tamaki, Yosuke Ota, Ryohei Egusa, Shigenori Inagaki, Fusako Kusunoki, Masanori Sugimoto, Hiroshi Mizoguchi, "Eda-Based Estimation Of Visual Attention By Observation Of Eye Blink Frequency", International Journal on Smart Sensing and Intelligent Systems., VOL. 10, NO. 2, June 2017, pp. 296-307.

Gsm based soldier tracking system and monitoring using wireless communication

- [3] Ismail Ben Abdallah, Yassine Bouteraa, and Chokri Rekik, "Design And Development Of 3d Printed Myoelectric Robotic Exoskeleton For Hand Rehabilitation", International Journal on Smart Sensing and Intelligent Systems., VOL. 10, NO. 2, June 2017, pp. 341-366.
- [4] S. H. Teay, C. Batunlu and A. Albarbar, "Smart Sensing System For Enhancing The Reliability Of Power Electronic Devices Used In Wind Turbines", International Journal on Smart Sensing and Intelligent Systems., VOL. 10, NO. 2, June 2017, pp. 407- 424
- [5] SCihan Gercek, Djilali Kourtiche, Mustapha Nadi, Isabelle Magne, Pierre Schmitt, Martine Souques and Patrice Roth, "An In Vitro Cost-Effective Test Bench For Active Cardiac Implants, Reproducing Human Exposure To Electric Fields 50/60 Hz", International Journal on Smart Sensing and Intelligent Systems., VOL. 10, NO. 1, March 2017, pp. 1- 17
- [6] P. Visconti, P. Primiceri, R. de Fazio and A. Lay Ekuakille, "A Solar-Powered White Led-Based Uv-Vis Spectrophotometric System Managed By Pc For Air Pollution Detection In Faraway And Unfriendly Locations", International Journal on Smart Sensing and Intelligent Systems., VOL. 10, NO. 1, March 2017, pp. 18- 49
- [7] Samarendra Nath Sur, Rabindranath Bera and Bansibadan Maji, "Feedback Equalizer For Vehicular Channel", International Journal on Smart Sensing and Intelligent Systems., VOL. 10, NO. 1, March 2017, pp. 50- 68
- [8] Yen-Hong A. Chen, Kai-Jan Lin and Yu-Chu M. Li, "Assessment To Effectiveness Of The New Early Streamer Emission Lightning Protection System", International Journal on Smart Sensing and Intelligent Systems., VOL. 10, NO. 1, March 2017, pp. 108- 123
- [9] Iman Heidarpour Shahrezaei, Morteza Kazerooni and Mohsen Fallah, "A Total Quality Assessment Solution For Synthetic Aperture Radar Nlfm Waveform Generation And Evaluation In A Complex Random Media", International Journal on Smart Sensing and Intelligent Systems., VOL. 10, NO. 1, March 2017, pp. 174- 198
- [10] P. Visconti, R. Ferri, M. Pucciarelli and E. Venere, "Development And Characterization Of A Solar-Based Energy Harvesting And Power Management System For A Wsn Node Applied To Optimized Goods Transport And Storage", International Journal on Smart Sensing and Intelligent Systems., VOL. 9, NO. 4, December 2016, pp. 1637- 1667
- [11] Youmei Song, Jianbo Li, Chenglong Li, Fushu Wang, "Social Popularity Based Routing In Delay Tolerant Networks", International Journal on Smart Sensing and Intelligent Systems., VOL. 9, NO. 4, December 2016, pp. 1687- 1709

[12] Seifeddine Ben Warrad and OlfaBoubaker, "Full Order Unknown Inputs Observer For Multiple Time-Delay Systems", International Journal on Smart Sensing and Intelligent Systems., VOL. 9, NO. 4, December 2016 , pp. 1750- 1775

[13] Rajesh, M., and J. M. Gnanasekar. "Path observation-based physical routing protocol for wireless ad hoc networks." International Journal of Wireless and Mobile Computing 11.3 (2016): 244-257.

[14]. Rajesh, M., and J. M. Gnanasekar. "Congestion control in heterogeneous wireless ad hoc network using FRCC." Australian Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences 9.7 (2015): 698-702.

[15]. Rajesh, M., and J. M. Gnanasekar. "GCCover Heterogeneous Wireless Ad hoc Networks." Journal of Chemical and Pharmaceutical Sciences (2015): 195-200.

[16]. Rajesh, M., and J. M. Gnanasekar. "CONGESTION CONTROL USING AODV PROTOCOL SCHEME FOR WIRELESS AD-HOC NETWORK." Advances in Computer Science and Engineering 16.1/2 (2016): 19.

[17]. Rajesh, M., and J. M. Gnanasekar. "An optimized congestion control and error management system for OCCEM." International Journal of Advanced Research in IT and Engineering 4.4 (2015): 1-10.

[18]. Rajesh, M., and J. M. Gnanasekar. "Constructing Well-Organized Wireless Sensor Networks with Low-Level Identification." World Engineering & Applied Sciences Journal 7.1 (2016).

[19] L. Jamal, M. Shamsujjoha, and H. M. Hasan Babu, "Design of optimal reversible carry look-ahead adder with optimal garbage and quantum cost," International Journal of Engineering and Technology, vol. 2, pp. 44–50, 2012.

[20] S. N. Mahammad and K. Veezhinathan, "Constructing online testable circuits using reversible logic," IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement, vol. 59, pp. 101–109, 2010.

[21] W. N. N. Hung, X. Song, G. Yang, J. Yang, and M. A. Perkowski, "Optimal synthesis of multiple output boolean functions using a set of quantum gates by symbolic reachability analysis," IEEE Trans. on CAD of Integrated Circuits and Systems, vol. 25, no. 9, pp. 1652–1663, 2006.

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[22] F. Sharmin, M. M. A. Polash, M. Shamsujjoha, L. Jamal, and H. M. Hasan Babu, "Design of a compact reversible random access memory," in 4th IEEE International Conference on Computer Science and Information Technology, vol. 10, June 2011, pp. 103–107.

[23] Dr. AntoBennet, M, Sankar Babu G, Suresh R, Mohammed Sulaiman S, Sheriff M, Janakiraman G, Natarajan S, "Design & Testing of Tcam Faults Using T_H Algorithm", Middle-East Journal of Scientific Research 23(08): 1921-1929, August 2015 .

[24] Dr. AntoBennet, M "Power Optimization Techniques for sequential elements using pulse triggered flipflops", International Journal of Computer & Modern Technology , Issue 01 ,Volume01 ,pp 29-40, June 2015.